

Knowledge Regarding Menstrual Cup among Nursing Students

Priya Mary Stella
Nehru College of Nursing

Abstract:- A descriptive study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding menstrual cup among student nurses in a selected college, kannur. A non experimental descriptive design was used in the study. The sample consisted of 40 nursing students from a selected college of nursing.

Data was collected by using the self administered questionnaire which comprised of 30 questions. Data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. The association between knowledge score and selected demographic variables was analyzed by chi square test.

The study findings revealed the knowledge level regarding menstrual cup, 3(7.5%) of student nurses had excellent knowledge, 19(47.5%) of student nurses had adequate knowledge, 16(40%) of student nurses had moderately adequate knowledge and 2(5%) of student nurses had inadequate knowledge, Since very few student nurses had excellent knowledge regarding menstrual cups slides on menstrual cup was shared to the participants to enhance their knowledge regarding menstrual cup.

Keywords:- Knowledge, Menstrual Cup, Student Nurses.

I. INTRODUCTION

Menstrual hygiene has a long, twisted history in India. Access to menstrual hygiene is related to gender equality in a crucial way; lack of bathrooms or sanitary napkins is one of the primary reasons why girls drop out of school. Whenever disaster hits, along with calls for food supplies and clothes, there is a demand for sanitary napkins. Yet, we were taxed (at 18 per cent GST) for our autonomy by the government until years of campaigning resulted in some relief in GST compensation.

India has the lowest penetration of sanitary napkins in the world. Reports by top business players in this segment (P & G, Johnson and Johnson) peg the penetration of sanitary napkins in India at 15-20 per cent of the population, though the government's National Family Household Survey claims higher penetration (national average of about 48 per cent in rural, 58 per cent in urban areas). Prices of products are still high: An average 5-7 day period costs an average of ₹88, a significant chunk of the daily minimum average wage rate at ₹180.

Enter the menstrual cup. I bought two cups at a discounted price of ₹500 (for both). One cup is supposed to last for five years. That works out to be about ₹8 a period. Several brands have entered the space, and a cup is priced anywhere between ₹500 and ₹1,000. Not to forget the huge environmental benefit to using the cup: One sanitary napkin can take around 500-800 years to decompose. Data from Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation shows that 28 per cent of pads are thrown in mixed waste and end in the landfill, 28 per cent are thrown in the open, while 33 per cent are disposed via burial and 15 per cent are burnt, even though the Solid Waste Management Rules 2016 clearly state that waste segregation has to be practiced at source. The rules also mandate that waste generators need to work with local administration and set up waste management systems for sanitary waste. Packaging waste also needs to be accounted for by the companies.

The truth on ground couldn't be further from this reality. Sanitary napkins and tampons also hold a risk of toxic shock syndrome, a rare but serious medical condition brought on by bacteria.

As already discussed above menstrual cup is being eco friendly, it is also cost effective, with a lifetime up to 10 years without any health hazards and less chance of vaginal irrigation and infection.. Extremely travel friendly and no need to be changed often. Also does not emit odor.

It is important to know what extent health care practices has been improved. There is a need for health care providers and educators to provide awareness on menstrual cups to girls and women. It is with this background, need and significance that a study was conducted to assess knowledge regarding menstrual cup among student nurses.

➤ Problem Statement

A study to assess the knowledge regarding menstrual cup among student nurses in a selected college, kannur

➤ Objectives of the Study

- Assess knowledge level regarding menstrual cup among student nurses
- Find out the association between the knowledge level regarding menstrual cup among student nurses and their selected demographic variables.

➤ *Hypothesis*

H1-There will be a significant association between knowledge level regarding menstrual cup among Student nurses and their selected demographic variables.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature was organized and categorized based on studies related to menstrual cup

III. METHODOLOGY

A non experimental descriptive design was adopted in the study. The sample consisted of 40 nursing students from Canossa College of Nursing, Cherukunnu.

Data was collected by using the self administered questionnaire which comprised of 30 questions. Data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. The association between knowledge score and selected demographic variables was analyzed by chi square test.

IV. FINDINGS

The study findings revealed that the knowledge level regarding menstrual cup, 3(7.5%) of student nurses had excellent knowledge, 19(47.5%) of student nurses had adequate knowledge, 16(40%) of student nurses had moderately adequate knowledge and 2(5%) of student nurses had inadequate knowledge. Since very few student nurses had excellent knowledge regarding menstrual cups slides on menstrual cup was shared to the participants to enhance their knowledge regarding menstrual cup.

The study findings revealed that the calculated chi-square value of all demographic variables like age, year of course, type of family, area of residence, educational status of mother, occupation of mother, age at menarche, currently used sanitary protection, prior information regarding menstrual cup and source of information are all less than the table value at 0.05 level hence, there is no association between knowledge level regarding menstrual cup among Student nurses and their selected demographic variables. Hence the formulated research hypothesis H1 is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted.

V. CONCLUSION

Menstrual cups can be the key to liberation and access to all sorts of wonderful things — education and a livelihood for instance — by freeing women in developing countries from being confined to their homes during their period. The municipality of Alappuzha in Kerala was the first civic body in India to distribute 5,000 menstrual cups for free, in an eco-friendly sanitation drive in 2019. Women's liberation? Hell yes! One can tell that a woman invented the menstrual cup.

In spite of the limitations of this study, this study shows that the menstrual cup can replace the other methods of menstrual sanitation. Increasing awareness in young girls can help to increase the utilization of menstrual cups.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Guidelines for management of sanitary waste. Available at: <https://kspcb.gov.in> › Sanitary Waste_ . Accessed on 06th August 2019.
- [2]. The mammoth task of managing menstrual waste in India. Available at: <https://www.downtoearth.org.in> › blog › health › the-mammoth-task-of-m. Accessed on 27th February 2019.
- [3]. Kaur R, Kaur K, Kaur R. Menstrual hygiene, management, and waste disposal: practices and challenges faced by girls/women of developing countries. *J Envir Pub Health*. 2018;2018. 4. Juma J, Nyothach E, Laserson KF, Oduor C, Arita L, Ouma C, et al. Examining the safety of menstrual cups among rural primary school girls in western Kenya: observational studies nested in a randomised controlled feasibility study. *BMJ Open*. 2017; 7(4):e015429.
- [4]. Mitchell MA, Bisch S, Arntfield S, Hosseini-Moghaddam SM. A confirmed case of toxic shock syndrome associated with the use of a menstrual cup. *Canad J Infect Dis Med Microbiol*. 2015 ;26(4):218-20.

➤ *E-Sources*

- [5]. [research-methodology.net](https://www.research-methodology.net)
- [6]. [Menstrual_cup_awareness_among_reproductive_women.pdf](#)
- [7]. [Mirit-sheila-Makena-pdf](#)
- [8]. [Raksha_suvarna_FINAL.pdf](#)
- [9]. [Study_of_adaptability_and_efficacy_of_Menstrual_cu\(1\).pdf](#)
- [10]. [VanEijKMenstrualcuplancet2019\(1\).pdf](#)
- [11]. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Research>
- [12]. <https://www.webmd.com/women/news/20190717/menstrual-cup-equal-pads-tampons->
- [13]. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/7/4/e015429>
- [14]. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpub/article/PIIS2468-2667\(19\)30111-2/Fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpub/article/PIIS2468-2667(19)30111-2/Fulltext)
- [15]. <https://reproductive-health-journal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12978-020-018-018-0>
- [16]. <https://reproductive-health-journal.boimedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12978-018-018-018-0>
- [17]. <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/7/4/e01529>
- [18]. <https://reproductive-health-journal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12978-020-018-018-0>
- [19]. <https://www.healthline.com>

➤ *Books*

- [20]. Denise E Polit and Cheryl Tatano Beck; *Nursing Research, principals and methods*, 7th edition; page no;109-111,157-158
- [21]. Dr. T. Vasundara Tulasi; *Nursing research and statistics*; 1st edition; Books ea publications; page no;147-150&354-355